

Evolved Open Clusters in the Gaia era: the case of Ruprecht 147

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Abstract

Open Clusters (OCs), and in particular the oldest ones, have been widely used to test formation and evolution theories of the galaxy. Also, since their HR diagrams provide an snapshot of stellar evolution, they are very good targets to investigate stellar formation and evolution models, together with dynamical interactions among stars. In particular, the most nearby ones profit from the best accuracies in astrometry, photometry and spectroscopy, and therefore they are commonly used as benchmark targets to assess performances of methods and calibrate results. Our project is devoted to perform an in-depth study of the physical properties of a sample of benchmark evolved clusters inside a radius within 500 pc around the Sun. Our aim is to revisit their properties of shape, radii, extinction, galactic velocity, age and chemical composition, using recent data release from Gaia, complemented with ground-based high resolution spectroscopic data.

Here we present the first results of this project after the release of Gaia DR2 concerning the cluster Ruprecht 147, the oldest nearby OC. We do a membership selection taking into account proper motions, parallax and photometry of the stars in a region of 4 deg radius around the center of the cluster. We study the peculiar kinematics of this cluster compared to the field stars in the solar neighbourhood. Finally, we do a spectroscopic analysis of the cluster using HARPS and HARPSN spectra for 5 main sequence stars and 6 red giants. We obtain preliminary chemical abundances for 8 species, pointing that the cluster has in general solar abundances.

1 Introduction

Open Clusters (OCs) are widely used to trace the history of the Galactic disk. Also, since their stellar populations cover a wide range of masses and evolutionary phases, their HR diagrams represent snapshot in stellar evolution. That is why they are ideal to test theories of stellar evolution. In particular, nearby OCs spanning different ages and chemical compositions are perfect targets to calibrate and validate astrometric, photometric and spectroscopic surveys.

The majority of them evaporate during the first 100 Myr of evolution. Internal interaction between members, encounters with giant molecular clouds and gravitational harassment by the galactic potential are the dynamical processes which contribute to the disruption of an OC. For this reason OCs which have survived these effects are valuable targets to understand them.

We have designed a project devoted to determine physical properties of the most nearby and evolved OCs in the light of Gaia data and combined with high precision spectroscopy and photometry. This will allow to investigate a handful of things: explore the outskirts of the clusters looking for tidal tails and escapees, which provide information about the disruption processes, and relate this to the chemical signature; explore how do the kinematical properties correlate with age and environment; among others. We also aim to provide to the community a comprehensive investigation of benchmark OCs to be used to validate and calibrate future studies and large surveys.

A particularly interesting cluster for our purposes is

Ruprecht 147. This is the oldest nearby (~ 3 Gyr, ~ 300 pc, Curtis *et al.*, 2013) cluster. It has very few detailed studies despite of its unique age-distance combination, which makes it a potential benchmark object for stellar and galactic astrophysics. We present here an analysis of this cluster revisiting its membership and kinematics in the light of Gaia DR2 data (Sections 2 and 3). We also do a preliminary analysis of its chemical composition using spectra of these member stars retrieved from HARPS and HARPS-N (Section 4).

2 Membership selection

We have used Gaia DR2 data (Gaia Collaboration *et al.*, 2018a) to perform a detailed membership selection using the methodology of Sarro *et al.* (2014). This consists in a multi-dimensional bayesian inference, from proper motions, parallax, photometry, and additionally taking into account uncertainties and correlations among the astrometric parameters.

We have queried a region of 4 deg radius in the sky around the center of the cluster $(\alpha, \delta) = (289.1^\circ, -16.3^\circ)$ to run the algorithm. This represents a radius of 30 pc at the distance of the cluster. We have found 227 members up to magnitude $G = 20$ with membership probability higher than 0.75. The color-magnitude diagram (CMD), and proper motions - parallax distributions are shown in Figure 1. A very well defined CMD is recovered, with a clear main sequence and a sequence of equal-mass binaries. Red giant branch and red clump are also present, as well as 17 white dwarfs. A lot of members has been recovered in the outskirts of the cluster as seen in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Member stars in Ruprecht 147 color coded by membership probability. Left: color-magnitude diagram using Gaia DR2 broad-band photometry; middle: proper motion - parallax distribution, right: proper motion - proper motion distribution.

3 Kinematics

In the light of Gaia DR2 data, we have analyzed the kinematics of this cluster with respect to the phase space distribution of the field stars in the solar neighbourhood. This study has already been published in (Soubiran *et al.*, 2018).

We computed heliocentric and Galactic cylindrical positions and velocities of the most nearby OCs, $d < 500$ pc. We have compared their distribution in the radial-rotational velocity plane with the one derived by Gaia Collaboration *et al.* (2018b) for field stars in the same volume around the Sun. In figure 8 of (Soubiran *et al.*, 2018) shows that most of the nearby clusters follow the bulk of the field stars distribution while Rup 147 stands isolated. Its radial motion towards the center of the Galaxy appears to be significantly higher than that of the other nearby clusters. However, this kinematical behaviour is compatible with the age of the Rup147 which belongs to the old thin disk known to have hotter kinematics.

4 Spectroscopic analysis

With the selection of members we have queried the HARPS and HARPS-N¹ spectrographs archives looking for high-resolution ($R=115,000$) and high SNR ($\gtrsim 50$) spectra. We have retrieved spectra for 5 main sequence stars and 6 red giants, analyzed also in Bragaglia *et al.* (2018). These are mainly located in the center of the cluster as can be seen in Figure 2.

We have used iSpec (Blanco-Cuaresma *et al.*, 2014a) to derive atmospheric parameters and abundances from spectral synthesis fitting using a grid of precomputed synthetic spectra available in the new version of iSpec (Blanco-Cuaresma *et al.*, in preparation). The derived $T_{\text{eff}} - \log g$ diagram is shown in Figure 3. Because of the high quality of the data, the errors in both parameters are very small, 0.04 dex in $\log g$ and 22 K in T_{eff} . Radial velocities are obtained from a cross-correlation with an atomic linelist mask, as seen in Figure 3

Figure 2: RA-DEC of the member stars found from Gaia DR2 (blue dots), spectra retrieved from HARPS and HARPS-N (orange and magenta squares, respectively), which correspond to MS and RG stars, respectively.

errors are all below 0.45 m s^{-1} , below 0.18 m s^{-1} in the case of the giants.

4.1 Chemical abundances

Abundances are obtained from spectral synthesis fitting using iSpec. In brief, it compares regions of the observed spectrum with synthetic ones generated on-the-fly using SPECTRUM (Gray & Corbally, 1994). The line selection was based on the automatic detection of absorption lines in the NARVAL solar spectrum included in the Gaia Benchmark Stars library (Blanco-Cuaresma *et al.*, 2014b). Each line was cross-matched with the atomic line list and we derived solar line-by-line chemical abundances using the reference atmospheric parameters for the Sun. Good lines lead to abundances similar to the solar ones (i.e. Grevesse *et al.*, 2007), thus we selected all lines with an abundance that falls in the range ± 0.05 dex. Atomic data is taken from the version 5 of the Gaia-ESO survey master line list (Heiter *et al.*,

¹HARPS is a high-precision echelle spectrograph installed on the ESO's 3.6m telescope at La Silla Observatory in Chile; and HARPS-N is the northern hemisphere counterpart installed at the 3.6m Telescopio Nazionale Galileo, located at the Roque de los Muchachos Observatory in Spain.

Figure 3: Left: $T_{\text{eff}}\text{-log } g$ diagram of the analyzed stars color coded by the SNR of the spectra retrieved.

2015) which covers the spectral range $4200 \leq \lambda \leq 9200$ Å, and contains atomic information for 35 different chemical species.

Abundances for 8 species (Ca I, Cr I, Fe I, Fe II, Ni I, Sc II, Si I, Ti I) are represented as a function of effective temperature and surface gravity in Figure 4 for both main sequence and red giant stars. In general the stars seem to have a solar composition in all analyzed elements except for Ca I, which is enhanced by 0.1 dex in mean. This would need further investigation to be confirmed.

Even though, in general, the errors in the individual abundances obtained from the line dispersions are low, we find some discrepancies among the chemical signature of the different stars of the cluster. Moreover, significant trends in abundance as a function of effective temperature and surface gravity are seen (e.g. in the case of Ca I, Fe I, Fe II, Ni I, Sc II). This is due, in part, to the different evolutionary phases of the stars in our sample, even inside the main sequence and red giant groups the range of T_{eff} and $\log g$ is large.

A way to mitigate this effect is to calculate abundances in a strictly line-by-line differential way. This technique consists in using a reference star (instead of the Sun) within the cluster which is in the same evolutionary state as the other stars. This would allow to reach a very high precision in abundances because it erases the differences that arise from slightly wrong atomic parameters in the lines, and other effects. To do this, we are on the process of observing more stars sharing very similar parameters to be able to make different groups. In this way, it could be possible to test the chemical homogeneity of the cluster. **how reference to hyades paper?**

5 Conclusions and future work

We present a preliminary study of the cluster Ruprecht 147 combining Gaia DR2 data and high-resolution spectroscopic data. This cluster is particularly interesting for its unique distance-age combination, which makes it a perfect candidate for being a benchmark object in stellar and galactic astrophysics.

A membership selection has been made using Gaia DR2

data in a very large region in the sky (4 deg radius) which corresponds to 30 pc at the distance of the cluster. We have found very probable members (probability larger than 0.75) at large distances from the cluster center. We have analyzed its kinematics in the context of the phase space distribution of the field stars in the solar neighbourhood. We have found that its radial motion towards the center of the Galaxy is larger than than of the thin disk stars.

The spectroscopic analysis is done using 11 HARPS and HARPS-N spectra retrieved from the archives. We have done the analysis using the tool iSpec. First, atmospheric parameters of the stars are recovered with small uncertainties. And then chemical abundances of 8 species are calculated using spectral synthesis fitting. Preliminary analysis shows solar abundances in almost all elements analyzed. Trends in effective temperature, and surface gravity possibly indicate an impact of the different evolutionary states of the analyzed stars in the abundances.

Further work can be done to improve the knowledge of this cluster. For example line-by-line differential abundances can be calculated in different groups of stars with similar atmospheric parameters to test the cluster homogeneity. New observations are currently ongoing to achieve this.

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References

- Blanco-Cuaresma, S., Soubiran, C., Heiter, U., & Jofré, P. 2014a, *A&A*, 569, A111.
- Blanco-Cuaresma, S., Soubiran, C., Jofré, P., & Heiter, U. 2014b, *A&A*, 566, A98.
- Bragaglia, A., Fu, X., Mucciarelli, A., Andreuzzi, G., & Donati, P. 2018, *ArXiv e-prints*.
- Curtis, J. L., Wolfgang, A., Wright, J. T., Brewer, J. M., & Johnson, J. A. 2013, *AJ*, 145, 134.
- Gaia Collaboration, Brown, A. G. A., Vallenari, A., Prusti, T., de Bruijne, J. H. J., *et al.* 2018a, *A&A*, 616, A1.
- Gaia Collaboration, Katz, D., Antoja, T., Romero-Gómez, M., Drimmel, R., *et al.* 2018b, *A&A*, 616, A11.
- Gray, R. O. & Corbally, C. J. 1994, *AJ*, 107, 742.
- Grevesse, N., Asplund, M., & Sauval, A. J. 2007, *SSRv*, 130, 105.
- Heiter, U., Lind, K., Asplund, M., Barklem, P. S., Bergemann, M., *et al.* 2015, *Physica Scripta.*, 90, 054010.
- Sarro, L. M., Bouy, H., Berihuete, A., Bertin, E., Moraux, E., *et al.* 2014, *A&A*, 563, A45.
- Soubiran, C., Cantat-Gaudin, T., Romero-Gomez, M., Casamiquela, L., Jordi, C., *et al.* 2018, *ArXiv e-prints*.

Figure 4: Chemical abundances $[X/H]$ as a function of T_{eff} (top) and $\log g$ (bottom) for 8 chemical species. Main sequence stars are colored in blue, red giants in orange.